

Unraveling the Intersection of Aging and Parkinson's Disease: A Collaborative Roadmap for Advancing Research Models

M Schmidt¹, AM Cuervo^{2,3}, KL Double⁴, D. Ehninger⁵, M Goldberg⁶, K Harvey⁷, JHJ Hoeijmakers^{8,9,10}, KC Luk¹¹, PG Mastroberardino^{12,13,14}, D Moore^{15,16}, LJ Niedernhofer¹⁷, LÉ Trudeau^{18,19}, D Jurk²⁰, JK Andersen^{1*}, I Bellantuono^{21 *}

Affiliations

¹Buck Institute for Research on Aging, Novato, CA, USA

² Institute for Aging Studies, Albert Einstein College of Medicine, Bronx, NY 10461, USA

³ Department of Developmental and Molecular Biology, Albert Einstein College of Medicine, Bronx, NY 10461, USA

⁴ Brain and Mind Centre and School of Medical Sciences (Neuroscience), Faculty of Medicine and Health, The University of Sydney, Sydney, Australia

⁵ Translational Biogerontology Lab, German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases (DZNE), Venusberg-Campus 1/99, 53127, Bonn, Germany

⁶ Department of Neurology, Center for Neurodegeneration and Experimental Therapeutics, University of Alabama at Birmingham, Birmingham, AL, USA

⁷ Department of Pharmacology, UCL School of Pharmacy, University College London, 29-39 Brunswick Square, London WC1N 1AX, UK.

⁸ Department of Molecular Genetics, Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Erasmus University Medical Center, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

⁹ University Hospital of Cologne, CECAD Forschungszentrum, Institute for Genome Stability in Aging and Disease, Joseph Stelzmann Strasse 26, 50931, Germany

¹⁰ Köln, Germany Princess Maxima Center for Pediatric Oncology, OncoCode Institute, Heidelberglaan 25, 3584 CS, Utrecht, the Netherlands

¹¹ Center for Neurodegenerative Disease Research, Department of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine, Perelman School of Medicine, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA, USA.

¹² Department of Molecular Genetics, Erasmus MC, Rotterdam, Netherlands

¹³ IFOM-ETS, the AIRC Institute for molecular Oncology, Milan, Italy

¹⁴ Università degli Studi dell'Aquila, L'Aquila, Italy

¹⁵ Institute for Cell Engineering, Johns Hopkins University School of Medicine, Baltimore, Maryland, USA

¹⁶ Neurology, Johns Hopkins University School of Medicine, Baltimore, Maryland, USA

¹⁷ Institute on the Biology of Aging and Metabolism, Department of Biochemistry, Molecular Biology and Biophysics, University of Minnesota, 6-155 Jackson Hall, 321 Church Street, SE, Minneapolis, MN 55455, USA

¹⁸ Department of Pharmacology and Physiology, Department of Neurosciences, Faculty of Medicine, Université de Montréal, C.P. 6128 Succ. Centre-ville, Montréal, Quebec H3C 3J7, Canada

¹⁹ Neural Signalling and Circuitry Research Group (SNC), Center for Interdisciplinary Research on the Brain and Learning (CIRCA), Center for Biomedical Innovation (CIB), Université de Montréal, C.P. 6128 Succ. Centre-ville, Montréal, Quebec H3C 3J7, Canada

²⁰ Mayo Clinic, Department of Physiology and Biomedical Engineering, Robert and

Arlene Kogod Center on Aging, Rochester, MN, USA

²¹ School of Medicine and Population Health, Healthy Lifespan Institute, University of Sheffield, UK

*Contributed equally to the work and corresponding authors

Corresponding authors

Julie K. Andersen

Buck Institute for Research on Aging

8001 Redwood Blvd

Novato, CA 94945

Email jandersen@buckinstitute.org

Ilaria Bellantuono

Healthy Lifespan Institute

School of Medicine and Population Health

Beech Hill Rd

Sheffield S10 2RX

Email I.bellantuono@sheffield.ac.uk

Abstract

Aging is the most significant risk factor for Parkinson's disease (PD), yet its role in PD pathogenesis remains underexplored. The challenges linked to modeling PD in commonly used rodent models, coupled with the prolonged timelines required for aging studies, have hindered progress in this critical area. The International Network for Parkinson's Disease Modelling and Aging (PD-AGE), funded by the Michael J. Fox Foundation, was established to address these challenges. Through collaborative efforts, PD-AGE developed a roadmap to reach consensus on experimental approaches, prioritize suitable models, and standardize protocols to investigate the intersection of aging and PD. This initiative advocates for prioritizing the crossing of mouse PD models with incomplete penetrance, including genetic (*Pink1*, *Lrrk2*, *Gba*) sporadic (α -synuclein pre-formed fibril) and environmental (paraquat) models, with well described accelerated aging models showing dopaminergic neuron vulnerability (*Ercc1*^{-Δ}, *Nfkb1*^{-/-}). We proposed that a tiered approach to experimental testing will enable systematic and rigorous characterization of these models, offering efficiency, economy, and further prioritization of model systems for testing specific hypotheses. By fostering collaboration and optimizing resource utilization, this roadmap provides a foundation for understanding the synergistic effects of aging and PD. It aims to accelerate mechanistic insights and refine preclinical models, ultimately supporting the development of interventions that address the aging-related dimensions of PD pathogenesis.

Main

Mouse models of Parkinson's Disease (PD) are invaluable for advancing our understanding of the disease and there is much hope that their use will help develop new therapeutic interventions. PD is a complex multisystem disorder characterized by a spectrum of motor and non-motor symptoms, and numerous mouse models have been developed to study its various aspects. While age is the primary risk factor for PD, the role of biological aging in PD is still unclear and it is often overlooked in the design and application of these models. This omission risks missing critical insights into disease mechanisms and opportunities for the development and translation of novel interventions, in particular as aging biology is emerging as a therapeutic target.¹

The International Network for Parkinson's Disease Modelling and AGEing (PD-AGE), funded by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research, was established to address critical gaps in our understanding of the role of aging in PD. Its creation was prompted by a workshop that brought together leading experts in PD modelling and aging who collectively highlighted the need for a systematic investigation into how aging contributes to PD². Insights into the mechanisms linking aging to PD remain limited and contradictory, making this research direction a high-priority. However, the complexity of PD, evidenced by the heterogeneity of patient phenotypes and the diversity of available preclinical models, along with the complexity of the aging process, which involves

multiple hallmarks and unfolds heterogeneously, poses significant challenges, which are more effectively addressed through a collaborative approach.

To achieve its goals, PD-AGE was divided into four working groups, each focusing on different models. Here we report on the working group that focused on approaches using mouse models and conducted a series of workshops to build consensus on prioritizing models of aging and PD, experimental approaches, and the standardization of protocols for their characterization. The result is a comprehensive roadmap for selecting optimal models, defining relevant measurements, and harmonizing protocols. This roadmap establishes a foundation for coordinated efforts, fostering resource sharing, knowledge exchange, and data integration to accelerate progress in understanding the intersection of aging and PD.

Parkinson's disease and aging.

PD is considered an age-related progressive neurodegenerative syndrome, including motor symptoms that are linked to gradual loss of dopaminergic neurons within the Substantia Nigra pars compacta (SNpc). The progressive nature of PD has been suggested to correlate not only with the continuing loss of dopaminergic innervation in the striatum but also with the spread of α -synuclein aggregates throughout the brain and in the periphery³. However, the causal role of α -synuclein aggregates in inducing neuronal loss and the broad range of symptoms associated with PD is a matter of debate⁴. Clinically, PD can be grouped into four general stages — prodromal, early, middle, and late. While it is classically characterized as a movement disorder, the prodromal phase, which can begin a decade or more before clinical diagnosis, is characterized by the emergence of multiple non-motor symptoms. Among them, alterations in smell (hyposmia), perturbations in sleep, autonomic dysfunction, general irritability and mood changes, as well as gastrointestinal disturbances such as constipation, are often reported. Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and inflammatory conditions, such as irritable bowel disease (IBD), are also frequent comorbidities of people diagnosed with PD. Some IBD patients carry mutations in Leucine-Rich Repeat Kinase 2 (*Lrkk2*) mutations^{5,6}. Bradykinesia (slowness of movement) represents the cardinal clinical diagnostic symptom⁷, and while tremor is commonly associated with PD, it is also present in other conditions and can result in misdiagnosis⁸. Confirmation of the diagnosis is therefore typically achieved by evaluating whether motor symptoms are alleviated upon administration of levodopa (usually as carbidopa/levodopa), a dopamine synthesis precursor. However, by the time motor symptoms appear, it is estimated that approximately 30% of dopaminergic neuron cell bodies have been lost in the SNpc and 50-70% of their axonal release sites in the caudate and putamen⁹. As PD progresses into the middle and late stages, more pronounced motor symptoms appear, including difficulty controlling limbs (stiffness, tremor, difficulty with movement initiation, limb extension), impaired balance leading to falls and fear of falling (FOF), dystonia, and increased autonomic dysregulation (low blood pressure, excessive sweating and salivation). Gastrointestinal symptoms also worsen and include constipation, sialorrhea, nausea/vomiting, weight loss, bowel incontinence, dysphagia, and incomplete emptying¹⁰. With further progression,

adjustments in pharmacotherapy are typically required. However, while increasing doses of levodopa or dopamine D2 receptor agonists often helps to improve motor symptoms, side-effects, including increased dyskinesia and neuropsychiatric issues can occur¹¹.

The prevalence of PD has risen markedly in recent decades due in part to ageing populations in many countries¹². While genetic factors likely play an aetiological role, most cases of PD are sporadic, with only 10% of PD patients presenting a known family history¹³. Mutations in genes such as *SNCA* (α -synuclein), *Pink1* (Pten-induced kinase 1) and *PRKN* (Parkin) are predominantly linked to early onset PD, whereas mutations in other genes, including *LRRK2* (Leucine-Rich Repeat Kinase 2) and *GBA* (glucocerebrosidase), are recognised contributors to mid and late-onset PD, respectively. In contrast, a mix of factors including age, genetic vulnerability, environmental exposures and lifestyle are associated with increased risk of disease in sporadic forms of PD.

Advancing age is the most significant risk factor for PD as evidenced by its markedly higher prevalence in older populations. The incidence rate increases from 41 per 100,000 among individuals aged 40–49 to 1,903 per 100,000 in those over 80 years old¹⁴. In addition, many age-related changes in the brain mirror those observed in the early stages of PD² and many of the hallmarks of aging — including mitochondrial dysfunction, impaired autophagy, increased inflammation, and cellular senescence¹ — have been shown to contribute to PD. A detailed review of studies investigating aging in *in vivo* models of PD by this network highlighted a complex and nuanced picture². While some models show clear evidence of age-related disease progression, others do not. Phenotypes shared with PD were particularly evident in models where slow disease progression could be tracked and when animals were observed over extended periods of time². These findings suggest that the influence of aging on PD is subtle, emerges gradually, and likely interacts synergistically with other contributing factors.

To advance our understanding of the role of aging in PD pathogenesis, the PD-AGE group emphasized the need for a more mechanistic approach. There was a strong consensus that crossing models of accelerated aging (reduced lifespan) or models with increased longevity (extended lifespan) with PD models would be a valuable strategy. This approach could clarify whether PD-like pathology can be either accelerated or slowed, shedding light on the systemic effects of aging underlying in PD. To develop a manageable plan of work, the group decided to prioritize studies that involved crossing models of accelerated aging with PD models, with the rationale that they could yield novel experimental tools useful to test interventions within shorter timeframes, while simultaneously providing critical mechanistic insights.

Selecting mouse models of Parkinson's disease

Our group previously conducted an in-depth review of available mouse models of PD², which informed the subsequent selection of representative models. The selection criteria prioritized models that capture the heterogeneity of the disease and represent

distinct categories of PD, including early and late-onset forms as well as environmental influences. Importantly, the focus was placed on models with incomplete penetrance and subtle PD phenotypes, excluding toxin-based models such as 6-OHDA (6-Hydroxydopamine) and MPTP (1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine) or models with genetic deletion of mitochondrial genes in dopaminergic neurons, that, although useful to study the impact of dopaminergic neuron loss, do not model a physiological trigger of PD. This deliberate approach aimed to assess potential synergistic effects when these models are crossed with models of accelerated aging. By using models with nuanced phenotypes, the group sought to determine whether such crossings amplify disease severity or accelerate the onset of PD-related characteristics.

The group strongly endorsed the Pten-induced kinase 1 (*Pink1*), knock-out (KO) mouse model, which involves the deletion or inactivation of the *Pink1* gene, mimicking the loss-of-function mutations seen in human patients. This model does not exhibit spontaneous overt neurodegeneration in the SNpc, even in aged animals, but develops mitochondrial dysfunction, subtle motor deficits (coordination and grip strength) and deficits in olfactory function and anxiety-like behaviors, commonly reported in the prodromal stages of PD. For these reasons *Pink1*^{-/-} mice are considered a model of the early, preclinical stages of PD. It was recognized that other genetic models of early-onset PD such as *Park2*^{-/-} (*Parkin*) mice could have also been selected, but it was felt that the *Pink1*^{-/-} mouse model has been more extensively characterised.

Representing models of later age onset PD, the *Lrkk2* and glucocerebrosidase (*Gba*) models had moderate to strong levels of endorsement as they represent common mutations in patients which display a slow progression and lack of full penetrance. LRRK2 is a large, multidomain protein kinase that plays a critical role in familial and sporadic PD¹⁵. Mutations in LRRK2, particularly the G2019S mutation, are the most common genetic cause of autosomal dominant PD and are also implicated in sporadic cases. *Lrkk2*^{G2019S} knock-in mice express the mutated protein at physiological levels, avoiding the potential overexpression artifacts obtained with transgenic models.¹⁶ Although they fail to recapitulate the full spectrum of PD pathology, including not showing extensive dopaminergic neurodegeneration and α -synuclein aggregation, these mice exhibit motor impairments and synaptic dysfunction. Mutations in the *GBA* gene, which encodes the lysosomal enzyme glucocerebrosidase (GCase), are a significant genetic risk factor for PD¹⁷. These mutations disrupt lysosomal function and autophagy, contributing to the accumulation of α -synuclein and neuronal dysfunction. Knock-in models exist which introduce specific human *GBA* mutations (e.g., D409V, L444P) into the mouse genome, mimicking pathogenic variants found in PD patients¹⁷. The D409V *GBA* heterozygous mutant mouse does not show signs of dopaminergic neuronal loss or accumulation of α -synuclein but it shows an increase in dopamine turnover in the striatum at 12 months¹⁸, considered one of the early signs of PD. The L444P *GBA* heterozygous mutant mice show progressive accumulation of total α -synuclein with age but no other sign of disease. However, they do show an increased vulnerability to the neurotoxin MPTP with increased loss of dopaminergic neurons in the SNpc compared to wild type mice after MPTP treatment, and a greater reduction in TH-fiber density and behavioral deficits which were exacerbated in *GBA*^{+/^{L444P} mice after MPTP treatment¹⁹.}

The α -synuclein pre-formed fibril (PFF) model was prioritized as a model of synucleinopathy in sporadic PD because it induces abundant aggregates immunoreactive for serine 129-phosphorylated α -synuclein, which is a selective marker of human synucleinopathy, although other α -synuclein models (e.g. viral overexpression of wildtype or mutant forms of α -synuclein) were recognized to display similar (~30-50%) loss of dopaminergic neurons. This model involves injection of sonicated fragments of fibrils generated from recombinant purified mouse or human α -synuclein into the brain or peripheral tissues of mice, thereby seeding the conversion of endogenous α -synuclein into fibrils and inducing a cascade of α -synuclein aggregation and pathology²⁰. This model mimics key features of sporadic PD, including the spread of α -synuclein pathology, intracellular inclusions resembling Lewy bodies, neuroinflammation, and partial dopaminergic neurodegeneration. The model also shows progressive motor impairments, including reduced coordination and bradykinesia, as well as non-motor symptoms characteristic of prodromal PD such as olfactory deficits and anxiety-like behaviors.

Among the environmental models, there was strong agreement on selecting the pesticide paraquat, considering its epidemiological relevance to PD and the induction of a phenotype that is intermediate in terms of severity relative to the very acute phenotype of MPTP or the very mild phenotype induced by rotenone, another pesticide^{21,22}.

Selecting Models of Accelerated Aging for Parkinson's Disease Research

The group undertook a rigorous process to shortlist mouse models of accelerated aging to study their interplay with PD. The primary selection criteria focused on models exhibiting multiple features of accelerated aging, including the presence of multi-organ dysfunction, multiple hallmarks of aging, and reduced lifespan (see tables 1-3 for a summary of these characteristics). Shortlisted models were Excision Repair Cross Complementation 1 knockout mice (*Ercc1*^{-/-}), Nuclear factor-kappa B p50 subunit knockout mice (*Nfkb1*^{-/-}), *Lamp2A* knockout mice (*Lamp2A*^{-/-}) and *Klotho* knockout mice (*Klotho*^{-/-}), all of which display systemic aging phenotypes. For the *Ercc1*^{-/-} and *Lamp2a*^{-/-} models, it was emphasized that a hypomorphic model is optimal where gene expression is attenuated rather than ablated and should be considered as a priority when available.

Additionally, the group explored the potential of other mouse models carrying alterations in DNA damage repair processes that are essential for neurons, such as *Ku70* mutants for non-homologous end-joining and Cockayne syndrome group A (*Csa* or *Ercc8*) mutants for nucleotide excision repair. *Ku70* and *Ercc8* have not been directly associated with PD yet, even though some evidence indicates an interaction between ERCC8 and Parkin²³. Moreover, both KU70 and CSA have been implicated in other neurological disorders²⁴⁻²⁷. Finally, *Ku70* and *Ercc8* mouse mutants display a mild phenotype, are amenable to breedings with mouse strains harboring PD genes mutations, and were therefore highlighted as promising candidates for bridging the gap between aging mechanisms and PD pathogenesis. The telomerase reverse

transcriptase knock out model (*Tert*^{-/-} and *Terc*^{-/-}), characterized by signs of accelerated aging across multiple tissues and shorter lifespan, was also considered. However, challenges in breeding and uncertainties surrounding the relevance of telomere shortening to brain aging raised concerns about its suitability for PD research.

Models related to mitochondrial dysfunction, such as the polymerase gamma gene mutator mouse model (*Polg* D257A/D257A), mitochondrial transcription factor A knock out mice (*Tfam*^{-/-}) and modified NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase core subunit S2 (*Ndufs2*^{-/-}), were also evaluated due to their common relevance to hallmarks of aging and PD but ultimately not endorsed. The limitations of these models included the limited evidence that they were models of accelerated aging (*Tfam*^{-/-} and *Ndufs2*^{-/-}), the segmental (tissue-specific) nature of their defects and the variability in the reproducibility of phenotypes (*Polg*^{D257A/D257A}). These constraints made them less suitable for comprehensive studies of systemic aging in the context of PD.

To refine the selection process, the models were ranked based on three criteria: (1) the presence of neuronal vulnerability or loss, (2) evidence of multiple hallmarks of aging, and (3) the occurrence of multi-organ dysfunction (Tables 2-4). This systematic evaluation ensures that the selected models not only represent accelerated aging but also provide relevance to PD, facilitating a more integrative understanding of the disease. All models show reduced lifespan²⁸⁻³¹. *Ercc1*^Δ, *Nfkb1*^{-/-}, *Lamp2a*^{-/-} and *Klotho*^{-/-} show dysregulation of multiple hallmarks of aging and dysfunction in multiple tissues. *Ercc1*^Δ, and *Lamp2a*^{-/-} show abnormalities in dopaminergic neurons in the SNpc and accumulation of α-synuclein. Analysis of dopaminergic neurons was not available for the *Klotho*^{-/-} mouse model. However, *Klotho*^{+/-} mice showed a significant decrease in the number of TH-positive neurons in the SNpc compared to that in WT mice³², changes in morphology and a significant decrease in striatal dopamine levels. *Nfkb1*^{-/-} did not show dopaminergic neuron loss *per se* but the number of TH+ neurons in the SNpc was reduced more extensively in these mice compared to controls when the mice were exposed to MPTP, suggesting increased neuronal vulnerability³³. We were unable to find information on neuronal vulnerability for the *Ku70*^{-/-} and *Csa*^{-/-} mouse models. Based on this information the group prioritized Excision Repair Cross Complementation 1 (*Ercc1*^Δ) and Nuclear factor-kappa B (*Nfkb1*^{-/-}) deficient models for crossing with PD models due to the richness of information available. *Lamp2a*^{-/-} and *Klotho*^{-/-} deficient mice could be considered as a close second. However, it was felt that *Ku70*^{-/-} and *Csa*^{-/-} are not sufficiently characterized at this time.

Optimizing Experimental Design for Characterizing Mouse Models of PD and Accelerated Aging

To establish an experimental framework for characterizing these aging PD mice, participants were provided with a comprehensive list of tests through a questionnaire, followed by group discussions. Tests were categorized into Tier 1, prioritized for all new crosses, and Tier 2 (Table 5), reserved for mouse lines showing accelerated or enhanced PD phenotypes based on Tier 1 tests. Selection criteria for Tier 1 tests

included invasiveness, resource intensity, timing, and the feasibility of longitudinal vs. cross-sectional assessments.

The consensus for Tier 1 tests included histological analysis with the counting of dopaminergic neurons in the SNpc, the quantification of striatal dopaminergic innervation loss and of α -synuclein aggregates, and two behavioral tests: the pole test (sensitive to dopaminergic neuron loss) and the catwalk gait analysis (if available) (Table 5). Additionally, stool frequency was included as a low-resource metric indicative of early PD symptoms. Decisions to proceed with further tests should be based on the outcomes of these initial assessments, with tissue storage for *omics* analyses prioritized for future studies. It was noted that the pole test and the catwalk gait test require a significant lesion to detect a phenotype; thus, the absence of behavioral changes should not preclude histological analysis.

Tier 2 tests included the examination of PD biomarkers in gut tissues or fecal samples, the quantification of sympathetic innervation through cardiac biomarkers, and the assessments of sleep disturbances, measures that are relevant to PD but requiring more resources (Table 5).

For experimental timing, the group agreed that pilot studies should be conducted at multiple time points, and tailored to the lifespan and PD characteristics of the specific model. Behavioral tests would be conducted prior to anaesthesia, intra-cardiac paraformaldehyde perfusion and culling of the animals, followed by histological analysis, including unbiased stereological counting of dopaminergic neurons in the SNpc and quantifying the density of dopaminergic innervation in the striatum using tyrosine hydroxylase immunohistochemistry to estimate axon terminal loss. Repeated pole testing on the same animal was discouraged due to the potential for learning effects, which could compromise reliability. The results of these studies are crucial to the design of the experiments for Tier 2 endpoints. We posit that this structured, phased approach balances accurate characterization with resource efficiency, optimizing the evaluation of these complex models.

Concluding remarks

In conclusion, aging represents a critical yet understudied risk factor for PD, warranting a concerted effort to bridge gaps in understanding the role of ageing biology in disease onset and progression. The complexity and heterogeneity of PD models, combined with the lengthy nature of aging studies, present challenges that require substantial resources and innovative approaches. The collaborative roadmap developed by experts in aging and in PD research aims to standardize methodologies, foster cooperation, and optimize resource utilization. The initial focus on combining selected PD models (e.g., *Pink1*^{-/-}, mutations in *Gba* and *Lrrk2* genes, α -synuclein PFF injection, and paraquat exposure) with accelerated aging models (e.g., *Ercc1*^{- Δ} and/or *Nfkb1*^{-/-}) offers a promising strategy to accelerate the discovery of novel insights into the interplay between aging and PD pathology.

This approach not only sets the stage for identifying key mechanistic links but also lays the groundwork for establishing preclinical PD models that incorporate aging as a central element of disease pathogenesis. By emphasizing tiered experimental designs, the proposed roadmap ensures a balance between depth of analysis and feasibility/economy. The proposed approach is anticipated to advance therapeutic testing and ultimately contribute to successful translation of strategies to delay or mitigate PD in patients. The collective vision layed out here is a future where aging-informed research propels the development of more effective interventions, transforming the understanding and treatment of PD.

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References:

1. López-Otín, C., Blasco, M. A., Partridge, L., Serrano, M. & Kroemer, G. Hallmarks of aging: An expanding universe. *Cell* **186**, 243–278 (2023).
2. Rocha, E. *et al.* Aging, Parkinson’s Disease, and Models: What Are the Challenges? *Aging Biol.* **1**, 20230010 (2023).
3. Braak, H., Rub, U., Gai, W. P. & Del Tredici, K. Idiopathic Parkinson’s disease: possible routes by which vulnerable neuronal types may be subject to neuroinvasion by an unknown pathogen. *J. Neural Transm.* **110**, 517–536 (2003).
4. Espay, A. J. & Lees, A. J. Loss of monomeric alpha-synuclein (synucleinopenia) and the origin of Parkinson’s disease. *Parkinsonism Relat. Disord.* **122**, 106077 (2024).
5. Maeda, T., Nagata, K., Satoh, Y., Yamazaki, T. & Takano, D. High Prevalence of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease in Parkinson’s Disease: A Questionnaire-Based Study. *Park. Dis.* **2013**, 1–6 (2013).

6. Herrick, M. K. & Tansey, M. G. Is LRRK2 the missing link between inflammatory bowel disease and Parkinson's disease? *Npj Park. Dis.* **7**, 26 (2021).
7. Kobylecki, C. Update on the diagnosis and management of Parkinson's disease. *Clin. Med.* **20**, 393–398 (2020).
8. Espay, A. J. *et al.* Essential pitfalls in “essential” tremor. *Mov. Disord.* **32**, 325–331 (2017).
9. Cheng, H., Ulane, C. M. & Burke, R. E. Clinical progression in Parkinson disease and the neurobiology of axons. *Ann. Neurol.* **67**, 715–725 (2010).
10. Bock, M. A., Brown, E. G., Zhang, L. & Tanner, C. Association of Motor and Nonmotor Symptoms With Health-Related Quality of Life in a Large Online Cohort of People With Parkinson Disease. *Neurology* **98**, (2022).
11. Taylor, J., Anderson, W. S., Brandt, J., Mari, Z. & Pontone, G. M. Neuropsychiatric Complications of Parkinson Disease Treatments: Importance of Multidisciplinary Care. *Am. J. Geriatr. Psychiatry* **24**, 1171–1180 (2016).
12. Dorsey, E. R., Sherer, T., Okun, M. S. & Bloem, B. R. The Emerging Evidence of the Parkinson Pandemic. *J. Park. Dis.* **8**, S3–S8 (2018).
13. Klein, C. & Westenberger, A. Genetics of Parkinson's Disease. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Med.* **2**, a008888–a008888 (2012).
14. Savica, R., Grossardt, B. R., Rocca, W. A. & Bower, J. H. Parkinson disease with and without Dementia: A prevalence study and future projections. *Mov. Disord.* **33**, 537–543 (2018).

15. Rui, Q., Ni, H., Li, D., Gao, R. & Chen, G. The Role of LRRK2 in Neurodegeneration of Parkinson Disease. *Curr. Neuropharmacol.* **16**, 1348–1357 (2018).
16. Chang, E. E. S. *et al.* LRRK2 mutant knock-in mouse models: therapeutic relevance in Parkinson's disease. *Transl. Neurodegener.* **11**, 10 (2022).
17. Smith, L. & Schapira, A. H. V. GBA Variants and Parkinson Disease: Mechanisms and Treatments. *Cells* **11**, 1261 (2022).
18. Polinski, N. K. *et al.* Decreased glucocerebrosidase activity and substrate accumulation of glycosphingolipids in a novel GBA1 D409V knock-in mouse model. *PLOS ONE* **16**, e0252325 (2021).
19. Yun, S. P. *et al.* α -Synuclein accumulation and GBA deficiency due to L444P GBA mutation contributes to MPTP-induced parkinsonism. *Mol. Neurodegener.* **13**, 1 (2018).
20. Sokratian, A. *et al.* Mouse α -s-ynuclein fibrils are structurally and functionally distinct from human fibrils associated with Lewy body diseases. *ScienceAdvances* **10**, 1–23 (2024).
21. Uversky, V. N. Neurotoxicant-induced animal models of Parkinson's disease: understanding the role of rotenone, maneb and paraquat in neurodegeneration. *Cell Tissue Res.* **318**, 225–241 (2004).
22. Meredith, G. E. & Rademacher, D. J. MPTP Mouse Models of Parkinson's Disease: An Update. *J. Park. Dis.* **1**, 19–33 (2011).
23. Pascucci, B. *et al.* Overexpression of parkin rescues the defective mitochondrial phenotype and the increased apoptosis of Cockayne Syndrome A cells. *Oncotarget* **8**, 102852–102867 (2017).

24. Enokido, Y. *et al.* Mutant huntingtin impairs Ku70-mediated DNA repair. *J. Cell Biol.* **189**, 425–443 (2010).
25. Tanaka, H. *et al.* HMGB1 signaling phosphorylates Ku70 and impairs DNA damage repair in Alzheimer's disease pathology. *Commun. Biol.* **4**, 1175 (2021).
26. Rass, U., Ahel, I. & West, S. C. Defective DNA Repair and Neurodegenerative Disease. *Cell* **130**, 991–1004 (2007).
27. Itoh, M. *et al.* Neurodegeneration in hereditary nucleotide repair disorders. *Brain Dev.* **21**, 326–333 (1999).
28. Weeda, G. *et al.* Disruption of mouse ERCC1 results in a novel repair syndrome with growth failure, nuclear abnormalities and senescence. *Curr. Biol.* **7**, 427–439 (1997).
29. Bernal, G. M. *et al.* Loss of Nfkb1 leads to early onset aging. *Aging* **6**, 931–942 (2014).
30. Bourdenx, M. *et al.* Chaperone-mediated autophagy prevents collapse of the neuronal metastable proteome. *Cell* **184**, 2696-2714.e25 (2021).
31. Kuro-o, M. *et al.* Mutation of the mouse *klotho* gene leads to a syndrome resembling ageing. *Nature* **390**, 45–51 (1997).
32. Kosakai, A. *et al.* Degeneration of mesencephalic dopaminergic neurons in *klotho* mouse related to vitamin D exposure. *Brain Res.* **1382**, 109–117 (2011).
33. Lin, S. *et al.* The regulation of NFKB1 on CD200R1 expression and their potential roles in Parkinson's disease. *J. Neuroinflammation* **21**, 229 (2024).
34. Wang, Z.-X., Li, Y.-L., Pu, J.-L. & Zhang, B.-R. DNA Damage-Mediated Neurotoxicity in Parkinson's Disease. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **24**, 6313 (2023).

35. Tilstra, J. S., Clauson, C. L., Niedernhofer, L. J. & Robbins, P. D. NF- κ B in Aging and Disease. *Aging Dis.* **2**, 449–465 (2011).
36. Taniguchi, K. & Karin, M. NF- κ B, inflammation, immunity and cancer: coming of age. *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* **18**, 309–324 (2018).
37. García-García, V. A., Alameda, J. P., Page, A. & Casanova, M. L. Role of NF- κ B in Ageing and Age-Related Diseases: Lessons from Genetically Modified Mouse Models. *Cells* **10**, 1906 (2021).
38. Kirchner, P. *et al.* Proteome-wide analysis of chaperone-mediated autophagy targeting motifs. *PLOS Biol.* **17**, e3000301 (2019).
39. Kaushik, S. & Cuervo, A. M. The coming of age of chaperone-mediated autophagy. *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.* **19**, 365–381 (2018).
40. Kaushik, S. *et al.* Autophagy and the hallmarks of aging. *Ageing Res. Rev.* **72**, 101468 (2021).
41. Buchanan, S., Combet, E., Stenvinkel, P. & Shiels, P. G. Klotho, Aging, and the Failing Kidney. *Front. Endocrinol.* **11**, 560 (2020).
42. Li, H., Vogel, H., Holcomb, V. B., Gu, Y. & Hasty, P. Deletion of Ku70, Ku80, or Both Causes Early Aging without Substantially Increased Cancer. *Mol. Cell. Biol.* **27**, 8205–8214 (2007).
43. Li, G. C. *et al.* Ku70: A Candidate Tumor Suppressor Gene for Murine T Cell Lymphoma. *Mol. Cell* **2**, 1–8 (1998).

44. Wang, H., Lautrup, S., Caponio, D., Zhang, J. & Fang, E. DNA Damage-Induced Neurodegeneration in Accelerated Ageing and Alzheimer's Disease. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **22**, 6748 (2021).
45. Madrigal-Matute, J. *et al.* Protective role of chaperone-mediated autophagy against atherosclerosis. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **119**, e2121133119 (2022).
46. Clemens, Z. *et al.* The biphasic and age-dependent impact of klotho on hallmarks of aging and skeletal muscle function. *eLife* **10**, e61138 (2021).
47. Novac, O., Matheos, D., Araujo, F. D., Price, G. B. & Zannis-Hadjopoulos, M. In Vivo Association of Ku with Mammalian Origins of DNA Replication. *Mol. Biol. Cell* **12**, 3386–3401 (2001).
48. Jaarsma, D., Van Der Pluijm, I., Van Der Horst, G. T. J. & Hoeijmakers, J. H. J. Cockayne syndrome pathogenesis: Lessons from mouse models. *Mech. Ageing Dev.* **134**, 180–195 (2013).
49. Jurk, D. *et al.* Chronic inflammation induces telomere dysfunction and accelerates ageing in mice. *Nat. Commun.* **5**, (2014).
50. Perez, K. *et al.* DNA repair-deficient premature aging models display accelerated epigenetic age. *Aging Cell* **23**, e14058 (2024).
51. Perez, K. *et al.* *ERCC1 Mice, Unlike Other Premature Aging Models, Display Accelerated Epigenetic Age.* <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2022.12.28.522011> (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.12.28.522011.
52. Sepe, S. *et al.* Inefficient DNA Repair Is an Aging-Related Modifier of Parkinson's Disease. *Cell Rep.* **15**, 1866–1875 (2016).

53. Dong, S. *et al.* Chaperone-mediated autophagy sustains haematopoietic stem-cell function. *Nature* **591**, 117–123 (2021).
54. Xilouri, M. *et al.* Boosting chaperone-mediated autophagy in vivo mitigates α -synuclein-induced neurodegeneration. *Brain* **136**, 2130–2146 (2013).
55. Goulielmaki, E. *et al.* Tissue-infiltrating macrophages mediate an exosome-based metabolic reprogramming upon DNA damage. *Nat. Commun.* **11**, 42 (2020).
56. Takayama, K. *et al.* mTOR signaling plays a critical role in the defects observed in muscle-derived stem/progenitor cells isolated from a murine model of accelerated aging: mTOR AND ITS ROLE IN PROGEROID MUSCLE STEM CELLS. *J. Orthop. Res.* **35**, 1375–1382 (2017).
57. Schneider, J. L., Suh, Y. & Cuervo, A. M. Deficient Chaperone-Mediated Autophagy in Liver Leads to Metabolic Dysregulation. *Cell Metab.* **20**, 417–432 (2014).
58. Nie, T. *et al.* Chaperone-mediated autophagy controls the turnover of E3 ubiquitin ligase MARCHF5 and regulates mitochondrial dynamics. *Autophagy* **17**, 2923–2938 (2021).
59. Zhang, W. *et al.* Ubiquitination of Ku70 by Parkin promotes apoptosis of lens epithelial cells. *FEBS J.* **290**, 3828–3842 (2023).
60. Okur, M. N. *et al.* Cockayne syndrome proteins CSA and CSB maintain mitochondrial homeostasis through NAD⁺ signaling. *Aging Cell* **19**, (2020).
61. Rovira, M. *et al.* The lysosomal proteome of senescent cells contributes to the senescence secretome. *Aging Cell* **21**, e13707 (2022).

62. Gurkar, A. U. & Niedernhofer, L. J. Comparison of mice with accelerated aging caused by distinct mechanisms. *Exp. Gerontol.* **68**, 43–50 (2015).
63. Yousefzadeh, M. J. *et al.* An aged immune system drives senescence and ageing of solid organs. *Nature* **594**, 100–105 (2021).
64. Karakasilioti, I. *et al.* DNA Damage Triggers a Chronic Autoinflammatory Response, Leading to Fat Depletion in NER Progeria. *Cell Metab.* **18**, 403–415 (2013).
65. Fielder, E. *et al.* Anti-inflammatory treatment rescues memory deficits during aging in *nfkb1^{-/-}* mice. *Aging Cell* **19**, e13188 (2020).
66. Wu, J. *et al.* Deficient chaperone-mediated autophagy facilitates LPS-induced microglial activation via regulation of the p300/NF-κB/NLRP3 pathway. *Sci. Adv.* **9**, eadi8343 (2023).
67. Qiao, L. *et al.* Deficient Chaperone-Mediated Autophagy Promotes Inflammation and Atherosclerosis. *Circ. Res.* **129**, 1141–1157 (2021).
68. Zhao, Y. *et al.* Klotho Depletion Contributes to Increased Inflammation in Kidney of the *db/db* Mouse Model of Diabetes via RelA (Serine)536 Phosphorylation. *Diabetes* **60**, 1907–1916 (2011).
69. Puebla-Osorio, N. *et al.* A novel Ku70 function in colorectal homeostasis separate from nonhomologous end joining. *Oncogene* **33**, 2748–2757 (2014).
70. Kajitani, G. S. *et al.* Neurovascular dysfunction and neuroinflammation in a Cockayne syndrome mouse model. *Aging* **13**, 22710–22731 (2021).

71. Van Der Lugt, B. *et al.* Akkermansia muciniphila ameliorates the age-related decline in colonic mucus thickness and attenuates immune activation in accelerated aging *Ercc1*^{-/ Δ 7} mice. *Immun. Ageing* **16**, 6 (2019).
72. Niedernhofer, L. J. Nucleotide excision repair deficient mouse models and neurological disease. *DNA Repair* **7**, 1180–1189 (2008).
73. Hansen, C. E. *et al.* Endothelial-*Ercc1* DNA repair deficiency provokes blood-brain barrier dysfunction. *Cell Death Dis.* **16**, 1 (2025).
74. Van Der Linden, J. *et al.* *Ercc1* DNA repair deficiency results in vascular aging characterized by VSMC phenotype switching, ECM remodeling, and an increased stress response. *Aging Cell* **23**, e14126 (2024).
75. Dollé, M. E. T. *et al.* Broad segmental progeroid changes in short-lived *Ercc1*^{-/ Δ 7} mice. *Pathobiol. Aging Age-Relat. Dis.* **1**, 7219 (2011).
76. He, Y. *et al.* Metabolomic analysis of dietary-restriction-induced attenuation of sarcopenia in prematurely aging DNA repair-deficient mice. *J. Cachexia Sarcopenia Muscle* **15**, 868–882 (2024).
77. Chen, Q. *et al.* DNA damage drives accelerated bone aging via an NF- κ B-dependent mechanism. *J. Bone Miner. Res.* **28**, 1214–1228 (2013).
78. Narasimhan, A. *et al.* The *Ercc1*^{-/ Δ} mouse model of XFE progeroid syndrome undergoes accelerated retinal degeneration. *Aging Cell* e14419 (2024) doi:10.1111/accel.14419.
79. Kim, D. E. *et al.* Deficiency in the DNA repair protein ERCC1 triggers a link between senescence and apoptosis in human fibroblasts and mouse skin. *Aging Cell* **19**, e13072 (2020).

80. Huerta Guevara, A. P. *et al.* Increased insulin sensitivity and diminished pancreatic beta-cell function in DNA repair deficient Ercc1 mice. *Metabolism* **117**, 154711 (2021).
81. Raza, Y. *et al.* Helicobacter pylori severely reduces expression of DNA repair proteins PMS2 and ERCC1 in gastritis and gastric cancer. *DNA Repair* **89**, 102836 (2020).
82. Henpita, C. *et al.* Loss of DNA repair mechanisms in cardiac myocytes induce dilated cardiomyopathy. *Aging Cell* **22**, (2023).
83. Doig, J. *et al.* Mice with skin-specific DNA repair gene (Ercc1) inactivation are hypersensitive to ultraviolet irradiation-induced skin cancer and show more rapid actinic progression. *Oncogene* **25**, 6229–6238 (2006).
84. Yousefzadeh, M. J. *et al.* Failure to Repair Endogenous DNA Damage in β -Cells Causes Adult-Onset Diabetes in Mice. *Aging Biol.* **1**, 20230015 (2023).
85. Valen, G. Signal transduction through nuclear factor kappa B in ischemia-reperfusion and heart failure. *Basic Res. Cardiol.* **99**, 1–7 (2004).
86. Cai, D. *et al.* IKK^N/NF- κ B Activation Causes Severe Muscle Wasting in Mice. *Cell* **119**, (2004).
87. O'Reilly, L. A. *et al.* Loss of NF- κ B1 Causes Gastric Cancer with Aberrant Inflammation and Expression of Immune Checkpoint Regulators in a STAT-1-Dependent Manner. *Immunity* **48**, 570-583.e8 (2018).
88. Correia-Melo, C. *et al.* Rapamycin improves healthspan but not inflammaging in *nfk1^{-/-}* mice. *Aging Cell* **18**, e12882 (2019).
89. Alvarez-Erviti, L. *et al.* Chaperone-Mediated Autophagy Markers in Parkinson Disease Brains. *Arch. Neurol.* **67**, (2010).

90. Xilouri, M. *et al.* Impairment of chaperone-mediated autophagy induces dopaminergic neurodegeneration in rats. *Autophagy* **12**, 2230–2247 (2016).
91. Akel, N. *et al.* Loss of chaperone-mediated autophagy is associated with low vertebral cancellous bone mass. *Sci. Rep.* **12**, 3134 (2022).
92. Kaushik, S. *et al.* Chaperone-mediated autophagy regulates adipocyte differentiation. *Sci. Adv.* **8**, eabq2733 (2022).
93. Reynolds, C. A. *et al.* Restoration of LAMP2A expression in old mice leads to changes in the T cell compartment that support improved immune function. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **121**, e2322929121 (2024).
94. Kuro-o, M. Klotho and the Aging Process. *Korean J. Intern. Med.* **26**, 113 (2011).
95. Sui, H., Hao, M., Chang, W. & Imamichi, T. The Role of Ku70 as a Cytosolic DNA Sensor in Innate Immunity and Beyond. *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.* **11**, 761983 (2021).
96. Nagtegaal, A. P. *et al.* Cockayne Syndrome Group B (*Csb*) and Group A (*Csa*) Deficiencies Predispose to Hearing Loss and Cochlear Hair Cell Degeneration in Mice. *J. Neurosci.* **35**, 4280–4286 (2015).
97. Cuervo, A. M., Stefanis, L., Fredenburg, R., Lansbury, P. T. & Sulzer, D. Impaired Degradation of Mutant α -Synuclein by Chaperone-Mediated Autophagy. *Science* **305**, 1292–1295 (2004).
98. Orenstein, S. J. *et al.* Interplay of LRRK2 with chaperone-mediated autophagy. *Nat. Neurosci.* **16**, 394–406 (2013).
99. Martinez-Vicente, M. *et al.* Dopamine-modified α -synuclein blocks chaperone-mediated autophagy. *J. Clin. Invest.* JCI32806 (2008) doi:10.1172/JCI32806.

100. Kuo, S.-H. *et al.* Mutant glucocerebrosidase impairs α -synuclein degradation by blockade of chaperone-mediated autophagy. *Sci. Adv.* **8**, eabm6393 (2022).

Mouse model	Disrupted gene
<i>Ercc1</i>^{-/-} <i>Ercc1</i>^{Δ/-}	Excision Repair Cross Complementation 1 (<i>Ercc1</i>) is a necessary component in multiple DNA repair pathways. A decline in DNA repair has been associated with age and in PD ³⁴ . The <i>Ercc1</i> ^{-Δ} hypomorphic mouse is engineered to produce a truncated version of the ERCC1 protein, lacking its C-terminal region, required to stabilize its binding partner XPF, the catalytic domain of the ERCC1-XPF DNA repair endonuclease. This truncation is achieved by introducing a premature stop codon into the <i>Ercc1</i> gene, resulting in a protein that is missing the last seven amino acids ²⁸ . The truncation weakens but does not abolish XPF interaction and ~5% of the normal levels of ERCC1-XPF are detected.
<i>Nfkb1</i>^{-/-}	Nuclear factor kappa (NF-κB) is a family of 5 hetero- or homo-dimeric transcription factors that regulate expression of 200 genes. <i>Nfkb1</i> is a gene encoding p105, a precursor protein that is processed into p50, a key subunit of the NF-κB family of transcription factors. NF-κB plays a central role in regulating immune responses, inflammation, cell survival, and apoptosis ³⁵⁻³⁷ .
<i>Lamp2a</i>^{-/-}	Chaperone-mediated autophagy is a selective form of autophagy that targets proteins bearing sequences with biochemical properties of the pentapeptide KFERQ for lysosomal degradation. KFERQ-like motifs are present in 50% of proteins, but may also be added through post-translational modification ³⁸ . The motif is recognized by the HSC70 chaperone protein that subsequently docks onto the CMA lysosomal receptor, the lysosomes-associated protein type 2A (LAMP2A) which mediates substrate translocation across the membrane. LAMP2A is the limiting component of CMA and ablation of LAMP2A leads to CMA blockage ³⁰ . While CMA can be stress-induced, it is also constitutively active in all cells ³⁹ . CMA decreases with age ⁴⁰ .
<i>Klotho</i>^{-/-}	Klotho encodes a transmembrane protein that functions as a co-receptor for fibroblast growth factors (FGFs), particularly FGF23 ⁴¹ .
<i>Ku70</i>^{-/-}	Ku70 is a protein encoded by the XRCC6 gene and is a critical component of the Ku heterodimer consisting of Ku70, Ku80. It is involved in non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) of double strand breaks ^{42,43} .
<i>Csa</i>^{-/-}	Cockayne syndrome group A protein, encoded by the ERCC8 gene. It plays a critical role in transcription coupled nucleotide excision repair, responsible for excising DNA lesions caused by UV light and many other endogenous base-pair-disrupting, transcription-stalling genotoxic adducts ⁴⁴ .

Table 1: Mouse models of accelerated aging shortlisted for ranking and combining with PD mouse models, along with the description of their gene function.

Ageing Hallmark	<i>Ercc1</i> ^{-/-} <i>Ercc1</i> ^{Δ/-}	<i>Nfkb1</i> ^{-/-}	<i>Lamp2a</i> ^{-/-}	<i>Klotho</i> ^{-/-}	<i>Ku70</i> ^{-/-}	<i>CSA</i> ^{-/-}
Genomic instability	*28	*35	*45	*46	*42,47	*48
Telomere attrition		*49		*46		
Epigenetic alterations	*50			*46		
Loss of proteostasis	*52		*30,53,54	*46		
Disabled macroautophagy	*55			*46		
Disrupted nutrient sensing	*56		*45,57	*46		
Mitochondrial dysfunction	*52		*53,58	*46	*59	*60
Cellular senescence	*28	*37,49	*61	*46		
Stem cell exhaustion	*62	*49	*53	*46		
Altered intercellular comm.	*63	*35,37				
Chronic inflammation	*64	*35,49,65	*45,66,67	*46,68	*69	*70
Dysbiosis [#]	*71					

Table 2. Hallmarks of aging identified in the six shortlisted accelerated aging mouse models. References provided experimental evidence of each hallmark, when available. [#] While dysbiosis was not measured in *Ercc1*^{Δ/-} mice, probiotic treatment was shown to improve mucosal lining and reduce inflammation.

Mouse model	Neurologic Abnorm.	Cardiac Disease	Kyphosis	Sarcopenia	Bone Loss	Organ Atrophy	Sensory Loss	↓body weight/fat	↓GI Function	Emphysema /Lung	↑Cancer	↓Immune function	Hair loss	↓Insulin sensitivity
<i>Ercc1</i> ^{-Δ}	+52,72,73	+74	+62,75	+62,76	+77	+62,75	+62,78	+82	+71,81	+82 %	+83 %	+63 %		+84 %
<i>Nfkb1</i> ^{-/-}	+65	+35,85		+35,86	+37,77			+49	+87	+88	+36,87	+29,49		
<i>Lamp2a</i> ^{-/-}	+30,54,89,90	+45,67			+91	+53		+92				+93		+45,92
<i>Klotho</i> ^{-/-}	+31	+31,41	+94	+46	+94	+94		+94		+94		+31,41	+94	+94
<i>Ku70</i> ^{-/-}	+24-27		+42						+43,69		+42 #	+42,95	+42	
<i>Csa</i> ^{-/-}	+70						+48,96	+70						

Table 2. Presence of age-related decline in organ function for the six shortlisted models of accelerated aging. References provide experimental evidence of each hallmark, when available. Neurological abnormalities include dystonia, tremors, ataxia, decreased neuronal function, reduced plasticity, cognitive impairment neurodegeneration and increased blood brain barrier permeability (*Ercc1*^{-Δ}); enhanced neuroinflammation and cognitive decline (*Nf-kb1*^{-/-}); gradual cognitive and motor deficiencies, gait disturbance and hypokinesia reminiscent of PD (*Klotho*^{-/-}); brain inflammation (Cockayne Syndrome (*Csa*^{-/-})). Organ atrophy includes skin, intestine, gonads, thymus, and/or bone marrow. # Indicates enhanced cancer incidence in *Ku70*^{-/-} dependent on mouse background. % indicates data derived from tissue-specific deletion of *Ercc1*.

Mouse Model	Evidence for Dopaminergic (DAergic) neuronal vulnerability
<i>Ercc1Δ</i>^{-/-}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERCC1 is necessary for DAergic neuronal function⁵² • Knockout specific to DA neurons (<i>Ercc1</i>^{-fl/fl}/DAT-Cre⁺) shows decrease in TH immunostaining in the SNpc and striatum at 26 weeks, with further decrease at 52 weeks as compared to control. • <i>Ercc1Δ</i>^{-/-} shows <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Decreased innervation of DAergic neurons in the striatum, but not the SNpc at 20 weeks of age. ○ Early increases in relative TH staining in the striatum hypothesized to be due to compensatory up-regulation to replace losses in dopamine occurring prior to frank cell loss. ○ Increased phosphorylation of α-synuclein (pSer129), an indicator of α-synuclein aggregation, but lack of detectable aggregates.
<i>Nfkb1</i>^{-/-}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Nfkb1</i>^{-/-} mice showed signs of brain aging, neuroinflammation, and cognitive decline that were rescued by Ibuprofen treatment⁶⁵, decrease in DCX positive neurons in the DG • <i>Nfkb1</i>^{-/-} mice exhibited exacerbated microglial activation and dopaminergic neuron loss after MPTP treatment³³.
<i>Lamp2a</i>^{-/-}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WT α-synuclein and LRRK2 can be targeted by CMA^{97,98} • A53T mutation⁹⁷ and chemical modifications by dopamine⁹⁹ as well as mutations in LRRK2⁹⁸ and GBA¹⁰⁰ all halt degradation via CMA leading to collapse of the neuronal metastable proteome³⁰ • Knock out of neuronal <i>Lamp2a</i> increases α-synuclein aggregates^{30,90}, which cannot be digested via CMA • Brain from <i>Lamp2a</i>^{-/-} mice recapitulate 42% of the changes observed in GBA-PD patients brains¹⁰⁰
<i>Klotho</i>^{-/-}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Klotho knockdown in 9.5 week mice³² resulted in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Significant decrease in the number of TH-positive neurons in SNpc compared to WT mice. ○ Much smaller TH-positive neurons in SNpc of Klotho mice than those in WT. ○ Reduced TH staining in the VTA but not in the LC. ○ Significant decrease in striatal dopamine levels, specific for the dopaminergic system. ○ Vitamin D restrictive diet (KI knock down mice have high levels of Vit D) increased number of TH+ SNpc neurons and restored dopamine levels similar to that of WT. ○ α-synuclein deposits were not assessed.

Table 4. Summary table highlighting studies supporting presence of DAergic neuronal cell vulnerability in the *Ercc1*^{-Δ}, *Lamp2a*^{-/-}, *Nfkb1*^{-/-} and *Klotho*^{-/-} models. The no evidence of DAergic neuronal vulnerability were found in *Ku70*^{-/-} and *Csa*^{-/-} models. TH = Tyrosine Hydroxylase; SNpc = Substantia Nigra pars compacta; pSer129=α-synuclein at Serine 129, DCX=doublecortin, DG=dendate gyrus, MPTP = 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine, VTA=ventral tegmental area, aKI-F=KI fragment, Vit D= Vitamin D, XP = Xeroderma Pigmentosum; CS = Cockayne Syndrome; DMV = Vagus nerve; OB = Olfactory bulb; LC= Locus Coeruleus; Snca = alpha-synuclein; WT = Wild Type; KI = Klotho; BBB = Blood Brain Barrier.

Tier 1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Stereological counting of SNpc DAergic neurons in histological sections •Assessment of striatal synaptic loss •Detection of α-synuclein aggregates •Pole test •Catwalk (if available at individual facilities) •Stool frequency
Tier 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Narrow beam/rotorod/hanging bar/inverted cage tests •Locomotor activity/open field tests •Histological assessment of degeneration in locus coeruleus •Immunohistochemistry to detect and quantify neurodegeneration in peripheral ganglia tissues •Examination of sympathetic innervation through specific cardiac markers •Anosmia/sleep disturbance/biomarkers in gut

Table 5. Tier 1 and Tier 2 priority tests for assessing PD characteristics in PD-aging mixed mouse models. SNpc = Substantia Nigra pars compacta